

Substituted Hydroxypyridines as Specific Reagents for the Microdetection of Osmium (VIII)

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Some substituted hydroxypyridines viz : 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP), 2, 3-dihydroxypyridine (DHP) and 3-hydroxypyridine-2-thiol (HPT) have been employed for the micro detection of osmium. Large amounts of most of the anions do not interfere, while interferences caused by some of the cations (including platinum metals), have been removed by using appropriate masking agents. Filter papers impregnated with AHP and HPT have also been developed for the purpose. The method, besides being simple and sensitive, can be recommended for the detection of osmium in the presence of other base and platinum metals.

COMPARATIVELY few reagents are available for the detection of micro quantities of osmium.

In most of the known methods, the interferences due to the associated platinum and other base metals pose a serious problem. In view of this, there is still a need for better reagents having better selectivity, sensitivity and stability, besides being easily procurable and inexpensive. The stepwise formation of blue and violet complexes of osmium with 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine¹ (AHP) and 3-hydroxypyridine-2-thiol² (HPT) was elucidated spectrophotometrically. It is now suggested that these two reagents along with one more substituted hydroxypyridine viz., 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (DHP) may be employed for the specific detection of osmium, when present alone or in the presence of other metal ions in the course of semi-micro qualitative analysis. Filter papers impregnated with AHP and HPT have also been recommended for the purpose.

Experimental

Reagents

Osmium (VIII) stock solution was obtained by dissolving an appropriate quantity of osmium tetroxide (Johnson-Matthey, U.K.) in about 100 ml of 2N NaOH solution, contained in a glass stoppered flask, as described by Ayres and Wells³. This was transferred into a measuring flask, the volume was made up to the mark by adding doubly distilled water and was further standardized iodometrically by the method of Klobbie⁴. The test solutions were obtained by diluting the stock solutions according to the requirements.

Reagents solutions (0.5% W/V) were obtained by dissolving AHP (Fluka AG, Switzerland), HPT (Fluka AG, Switzerland) and DHP (Aldrich Chemicals Co., U.S.A.) in ethanol.

All other reagents used were of reagent grade. Anions were used in the form of their sodium or

potassium salts, while cations were taken as sulphates and nitrates. All these solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. For measuring the small volumes of the drops, an Alga Micrometer syringe has been used. Graduated droppers were used for adding solutions of various interfering ions in known amounts.

Procedure

The test is carried out by placing a drop of the test solution containing osmium(VIII) with micrometer syringe on a spot plate or a filter paper (Whatman No. 1) followed by a drop of the reagent solution (AHP or HPT) and two drops of acetic acid (50% V/V) solution, when a green colour develops instantaneously, indicating the presence of osmium. The green colour further changes to violet on addition of 2-3 drops of NaOH (50% W/V) thereby confirming the identity of osmium in the test solution. In case of DHP, the test is carried out by taking a drop of the test solution in a micro test tube, followed by a drop of the reagent (DHP) and sodium hydroxide each. An orange colour develops on slightly warming the mixture, indicating the presence of osmium in the test solution. To study the effect of diverse ions, a drop of osmium stock solution (5 ppm), is mixed with a drop of reagent solution (AHP, HPT or DHP) and a drop of the solution of foreign ion (of varying concentrations) and proceeded as described above. The colour obtained is compared with a blank (prepared under identical conditions but containing no foreign ion).

Limit of identification : 0.08 γ with AHP; 0.095 γ with HPT and 0.034 γ with DHP on a spot plate.

Limit of dilution : 1 : 62,50,00 with AHP and 1 : 5,300,00 and 1 : 14,700,00 with HPT and DHP respectively.

Osmium test paper (OTP)

Whatman filter paper No. 1 was soaked for 15–20 min in 1% (W/V) solution of AHP or HPT. The paper was taken out, dried at room temperature and cut into strips of required size.

A drop of the test solution is placed on the osmium test paper and a drop of acetic acid (50%) is added to it, when an instantaneous appearance of green spot, which turns violet on addition of 2 drops of sodium hydroxide (50%), confirms the identity of osmium.

Minimum concentration of osmium solution which gives green spot to test paper is 2.4γ with the limit of dilution of 1 : 20,000.

Results and Discussion

The effect of various interfering ions has been studied in detail. The following table records the

TABLE 1. TOLERANCE LIMITS OF VARIOUS IONS IN THE DETECTION OF OSMIUM

Ion added	Amount of osmium taken = 5 ppm		
	Tolerance limit using		
	AHP (ppm)	DHP (ppm)	HPT (ppm)
Oxalate	2,000	1,500	1,500
Citrate	1,000	+	750
Borate	2,000	1,000	1,500
Phosphate	2,000	2,000	1,500
Nitrite	500	400	500
Bromide	2,000	1,000	750
Chloride	2,000	2,000	1,200
Fluoride	1,500	1,000	1,000
Tartrate	2,000	+	1,000
Iodide	1,500	1,500	1,000
Thiourea	*	*	*
Thiosulphate	*	*	*
Thiocyanate	*	*	*
Persulphate	2,000	2,000	1,800
Ru ³⁺	5	10	5
Rh ³⁺	8	10	7
Pd ²⁺	20	10	16
Pt ⁴⁺	40	15	30
Ir ³⁺	40	20	30
Fe ³⁺	*	*	*
Co ³⁺	10	8	6
Ni ²⁺	5	5	4
Zn ²⁺	10	10	8
Cd ²⁺	20	25	15
Hg ²⁺	60	75	50
Al ³⁺	5	3	4
Cu ²⁺	10	10	7
Ba ²⁺	150	175	120
Sc ³⁺	16	20	10
Mn ²⁺	15	15	10
V ⁶⁺	13	15	9
Pb ²⁺	50	50	42
Sn ⁴⁺	*	*	*
EDTA	550	+	40

* Interferes seriously.

tolerance limits of the various ions. It was observed that some ions such as thiourea, thiosulphate and thiocyanate interfere seriously and inhibit the colour formation even when present in small amounts.

Removal of interferences

Interferences caused by platinum metals and some other metal ions were circumvented by means of EDTA and other masking agents (amounts of ppm given in the parentheses) as shown below :

Ru³⁺(40), Rh³⁺(40), Pd²⁺(40), Ir³⁺(40), Pt⁴⁺(40), Pb²⁺(150) and Ba²⁺(130) with EDTA; Hg²⁺(120) and Cd²⁺(150) with iodide and Mn²⁺(110) with fluoride.

Test by activation of chlorate solutions is widely used for the detection of osmium and ruthenium^{5,6}. The limit of identification is 0.005γ with the dilution limit of 1 : 10⁷. However, this test can be modified and made specific by utilizing the volatility of OsO₄ (limit of identification = 0.01γ and dilution limit = 1 : 5 × 10⁶), but the disadvantage lingering with this method is that the associated platinum metals interfere and it is required to collect the volatile OsO₄ which is really a cumbersome process. However, despite these difficulties the method still remains one of the sensitive methods employed for the detection of metal. The other commonly used reagent for the detection of osmium is benzidine acetate (in saturated solution)⁷, but the process is lengthy and sensitivity is much less (identification limit = 0.04γ).

3,3'-dimethylnaphthidine⁸ is another reagent which has been employed to detect osmium taken in the presence of potassium chlorate (identification limit = 10⁻⁵γ). This test is highly pH-dependent and the colour becomes maximum at pH 2.3 and also depends upon temperatures and reagent concentration. Amorphine and *p*-phenylenediamine have also been used instead of 3,3'-di-methylnaphthidine.

The present method is simple and selective and it is free from the difficulty with which one is confronted while handling the volatile OsO₄. In case of AHP and HPT an instantaneous colour takes place in cold, while slight warming is necessary in case of DHP. Considerable amounts of platinum and base metals can be masked in case of AHP. Filter papers impregnated with AHP and HPT have also been recommended for this purpose. The reagents compare favourably with some of the reagents utilized for the detection of osmium. The reagents used are inexpensive and easily procurable, and the method can be successfully utilized for the qualitative detection of osmium in semi-microanalysis scheme.

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